

MOBILE APPLICATION FOR CALCULATION OF ELECTRICAL CIRCUITS USING THE GAUSS ELIMINATION METHOD

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Summary – In this article we present the development of an application for Android mobile devices that facilitates the calculation of electrical circuits. We use the Gauss elimination method in the application to perform the calculations and it allows students to visualize the circuits before performing the calculations. You can use the application as a tool to assist in the teaching of electrical circuits. It is simple to use and allows students to solve circuit problems more quickly and efficiently.

Keywords: Technological Education; Gauss Elimination Method; Calculation of Electrical Circuits; Systems of Linear Equations; Android Application.

INTRODUCTION

Engineering and physics training fundamentally involves studying electrical circuits. However, it can be complex and time-consuming to solve circuit problems. Recently, educators have found technology to be a valuable tool in assisting the learning process [1]. In particular, mobile applications can potentially provide an interactive platform for problem-solving and visualization of concepts [1].

In this context, we present the development of a mobile application for Android devices that facilitates the calculation of electrical circuits in this article. To perform calculations, the application uses the Gauss elimination method, a widely used numerical method for solving systems of linear equations [2]. Additionally, students can visualize circuits before performing calculations using it. Previous works [3] have explored the use of the Gauss elimination method in electrical circuits. However, our contribution is implementing this method in a mobile application. The application can assist in teaching electrical circuits and allow students to solve circuit problems more quickly and efficiently.

DEVELOPMENT

We began developing the application with an in-depth study on the fundamental concepts of electrical circuits [4] and [1] and the Gauss elimination method [5], [6], and [7]. The application operates based on electrical circuits, which are uninterrupted paths of conductive material that allow for the continuous flow of charge carriers.

Also known as the scaling method, the Gauss elimination method is an algorithm for solving systems of linear equations [2] and [3]. This method applies successive elementary operations on a linear system to transform it into a system that's easier to solve, which has exactly the same solutions as the original [3]. Elementary operations involve swapping two rows with each other, multiplying all elements of a row by a non-zero constant, and replacing a row by its sum with a multiple of another row [5], [6], and [7]. Fig. 1 uses the Gauss elimination method to present the resolution.

$$\begin{pmatrix} a^{(1)}_{11} & a^{(1)}_{12} & a^{(1)}_{13} \\ 0 & a^{(2)}_{22} & a^{(2)}_{23} \\ 0 & 0 & a^{(3)}_{33} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \\ I_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} b^{(1)}_1 \\ b^{(2)}_2 \\ b^{(3)}_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$x_n = \frac{b_n^{(n)}}{a_{nn}^{(n)}}$$

$$x_k = (b_k^{(k)} - \sum_{j=k+1}^n a_{kj}^{(k)} x_j) / a_{kk}^{(k)}$$

Figure 1 – Gauss elimination method [8].

In the context of the application, we use the Gauss elimination method to solve linear systems that represent electrical circuits. We represent the system's equations as matrices and perform elementary operations on these matrices to find a solution.

When analyzing electrical circuits [8], we use matrices to provide a compact and efficient representation of linear systems. In the matrix, each row represents an equation in the system, and each column represents a variable. The elements of the matrix are coefficients of variables in equations. Fig. 3 shows an example of systems with matrices that we used for testing the model shown in Fig. 4.

$$\begin{bmatrix} R_1 & -R_2 & 0 \\ 0 & R_2 & R_3 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \\ I_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} E_1 - E_2 \\ E_2 + E_3 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 2 – Circuit modeling [8]

$$(A) \begin{bmatrix} 2 & -3 & 0 \\ 0 & 3 & 5 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \\ I_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -4 \\ 21 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$(B) \begin{bmatrix} 4 & -5 & 0 \\ 0 & 5 & 7 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \\ I_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -7 \\ 20 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$(C) \begin{bmatrix} 6 & -12 & 0 \\ 0 & 12 & 7 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \\ I_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -6 \\ 24 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 3 – Input parameters [8]

In the case of electrical circuits, we typically use variables to represent currents or voltages in different parts of the circuit. The properties of circuit components, like resistances and capacitances, determine the coefficients in the matrix.

Fig. 4 shows an example of an electrical circuit, and Fig. 5 demonstrates our allocation of the Matrix and Vector in computer memory.

Figure 4 – Circuit Example [8]

Figure 5 – Array Allocation in Computer Memory [8]

We implemented the application using the C# programming language in Visual Studio [9] software for mobile applications, a tool widely used for developing Android applications. We implemented the Gauss elimination method using matrices and basic mathematical operations.

Subsequently, we performed the application's modeling, defining its functionalities and how the user interface would appear, as shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6 – eGauss user interface [8]

Users can input the values of circuit components, such as resistances and voltages, into the application, which then automatically performs the calculations. Additionally, users can use a feature in the application to visualize the circuits before carrying out the calculations, which aids in understanding the problem.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results show that the application can accurately calculate the values of electrical circuits and provide a user-friendly interface.

TABLE 1 – Input values.

System	E1	E2	E3	R1	R2	R3
A	10	14	7	2	3	5
B	5	12	8	4	5	7
C	3	9	15	6	12	7

TABLE 2 – Output values.

System	I1	I2	I3
A	1	2	3
B	0,1928	1,5542	1,7470
C	0,8788	0,9394	1,8182

TABLE 3 – eGauss output values.

System	I1	I2	I3
A	1	2	3
B	0,1927	1,5542	1,7469
C	0,8787	0,9393	1,8181

We conducted manual calculations of current values (I1, I2, I3) for systems A, B, and C based on input values (E1, E2, E3, R1, R2, R3), as shown in the analysis of Table 1 and Table 2. Table 2 presents the results we obtained. Similarly, Table 3 presents the results that the application obtained. We used the input coefficients identical to those in Table 1 to calculate currents in the application.

A comparison of Table 2 and Table 3 reveals that the manually calculated values and the application-calculated values are very close. Rounding or numerical precision may cause small variations. This validation confirms the application's effectiveness in accurately calculating electrical circuit values.

Moreover, students can use the application not only to facilitate their learning process by solving circuit problems more quickly and efficiently but also to provide a quick and easy way to check manual calculations. This underscores the application's role as a useful tool for assisting in teaching electrical circuits.

However, it's important to note that while we can use the application as a complementary tool to traditional teaching methods, it shouldn't completely replace theoretical and practical lessons. Nevertheless, it represents how students can significantly advance their learning about electrical circuits.

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